

THE RELATION OF 24-HOUR URINE "LIPOCALIN-2" LEVELS WITH LABORATORY AND CLINICAL PARAMETERS IN CHILDHOOD OBESITY

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To cite this article: Aydin CELIK, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 3-5, 2023, p. 88 – 156. -
0099-0001-2303-0105.

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("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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THANKS

Special thanks to all my teachers who contributed to my education during my Pediatric Health and Diseases specialization education, to my esteemed Clinical Chief and Thesis Advisor Assoc. To Dr Ayhan ABACI,

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To my friends who have always been by my side and all my assistants who supported me during this difficult process, and to Specialist Dr. Ayşe Derya BULUŞ, who did not spare her help while preparing my thesis,

T.C.S.B., who did not spare his help while preparing my thesis. To Dr Cemile KOCA from Ankara Atatürk Training and Research Hospital, Department of Biochemistry,

To my dear parents, my brother Erkan ÇELİK and my sister Lütfiye ÇELİK, who have always been by my side and supported me throughout my entire education life,

With endless respect, love and thanks to my fiancée Büşra KARADAĞ, who will accompany me on the journey of a lifetime.

Dr. Aydın CELİK

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ABBREVIATIONS

- AGRP** : Aagouti related protein
ASP : Acylation-stimulating protein
CCK : Cholecystokinin
CRF : Corticotropin releasing factor
DEXA : Dual energy x-ray absorptiometry
DM : Diabetes mellitus
GLP-1 : Glucagon like peptide-1
5-HT : 5-Hydroxytryptamine
HDL : High-density lipoprotein
HOMA-IR : Homeostasis Model Assessment- Insulin Resistance
IGF-1 : Insulin like growth factor-1
IL-6 : Interleukin-6
IR : Insulin resistance
IVGTT : Intravenous glucose tolerance test
LCN-2 : Lipocalin-2
LDL : Low-density lipoprotein
LHA : Lateral hypothalamic nucleus
mRNA : messenger Ribonucleic Acid
MCH : Melanin concentrating hormone
NGAL : Neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin
NL : Neutrophil lipocalin
NHANES : National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
NPY : Neuropeptide – Y
OGTT : Oral glucose tolerance test
PAI-1 : Plasminogen activator inhibitor-1
PCOS : Polycystic ovary syndrome
POMC : Pro-opiomelanocortin
SD : Standard Deviation
FFA : Free fatty acid
TG : Triglyceride
TNF- α : Tumor necrosis factor-alpha

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BMI : Body Mass Index

VLDL: Very Low-Density Lipoprotein

VMH: Ventromedial hypothalamic nucleus

ABSTRACT

Aim: A growing number of children throughout the globe are overweight or obese, which raises concerns about future rates of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and cancer. Lipocalin-2, also known as LCN-2, is a glycoprotein that has been studied for more than ten years. It is well established that it rises in response to stressful circumstances, such as the presence of neoplastic disease, infection, inflammation, or ischemia. In recent years, several research have been conducted with the hypothesis that LCN 2 may serve as an early biomarker of renal ischemia. The purpose of this research is to evaluate the relationship between 24-hour urine LCN 2 levels and laboratory and clinical indicators in children who are overweight or obese.

Method: Participants in our research ranged in age from 11 to 16 years old, and there was a total of 43 healthy obese participants and 32 healthy non-obese participants. We conducted anthropometric examinations and measurements. We examined the levels of cholesterol, LDL, and HDL in the blood as well as fasting serum glucose and insulin. The ELISA technique was used to assess the amounts of LCN 2 in urine collected over a period of 24 hours. The results of the analysis of the data gathered from this research were conducted using SPSS 15.0. We used Pearson correlation analyses to investigate the relationship between the independent factors. For the comparison between the obese group and the control group, a p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Results: The levels of lipocaline and creatinine in the obese people's urine were significantly different from those in the control group after 24 hours (p 0.05). When we compare groups of obese people who are insulin resistant with obese people who are not insulin resistant, we find that the insulin resistant obese group has considerably higher 24-hour urine LCN 2 levels. (p<0.05)

Conclusion: There may be a connection between insulin resistance and LCN 2 in urine collected over a 24-hour period in children who are obese. More research is necessary, both in youngsters and in large populations, for us to comprehend the part that LCN 2 plays in obesity.

Keywords: *Childhood, Obesity, Lipocalin-2, NGAL*

1. INTRODUCTION AND PURPOSE

Obesity is a significant public health issue that affects 25-30% of children and adolescents in the United States. Children who, twenty years ago, spent their free time playing in the gardens or on the streets now spend their time in front of the television and computer because of the development of technology and the changing social structure. Along with the shift in their eating habits, this has led to an increase in the prevalence of obesity in children and adolescents.

The frequency of childhood obesity is rising all throughout the globe, particularly in developed nations, especially in industrialized countries. The risk of obesity in children and adolescents is highest during the first year of life, between the ages of 5 and 6, and again throughout adolescence. As they reach adulthood, thirty percent of obese children and eighty percent of obese adolescents are still fat. On the other hand, it is well knowledge that the origin of obesity in adulthood may be traced back to infancy in as many as thirty percent of cases. (4) Together with the growth of industry, it seems that the change from a physically power-based lifestyle to a sedentary lifestyle and the intake of foods containing intensive calories are the primary reasons for this rise in the incidence of obesity in the previous ten to twenty years. (5) Obesity in children, which is on the rise at an epidemic rate, is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease (including arterial hypertension, atherosclerosis, ischemic heart disease, and heart failure), renal disease, and metabolic illness (hyperlipidemia, hyperinsulinemia, diabetes, hyperuricemia, etc.) The development of difficulties connected to obesity has been attributed to a substantial number of possible pathways. It has been speculated that the adipokines that are released from adipose tissue are the most significant contributors to this process. Not only does adipose tissue serve the function of providing an energy reserve and storing triglycerides, but it also functions as a tissue that produces leptin, tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), adiponectin, acylation-stimulating protein (ASP), resistin, interleukin-6 (IL-6), and plasminogen activator. In addition to this, it performs the function of a tissue that is accountable for the production and release of many mediators, including inhibitor-1 (PAI-1) and transforming growth factor-b (TGF-b).

It is a glycoprotein, also called NL (neutrophil lipocalin), a protein belonging to the lipocalin family, which consists of more than 20 proteins. Lipocalin-2 (LCN 2) is a 25 kDa NGAL (neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin) that is secreted from liver and adipose tissue. NGAL stands for neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin.

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Although evidence of its existence dates back more than ten years, the physiological make-up of this organism is still not completely understood (6,7). It is well established that it rises in intensity in the presence of stressful conditions such as infection, inflammation, ischemia, and neoplastic disease. In recent years, a variety of research have been conducted with the hypothesis that it might be an early indicator of renal ischemia. [Citation needed] LCN 2 has been shown to be the most investigated and potentially useful biomarker for the diagnosis of acute renal failure in both clinical and experimental trials (8).

Insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes mellitus are both conditions that may be caused by obesity, which is a well-known risk factor (type 2 DM). In addition, the presence of obesity has been linked to glomerular hyperfiltration, the development of glomerulosclerosis, and kidney failure that are not correlated with diabetes. It has been observed that renal endothelial dysfunction and increased renin-angiotensin system activity have a role in the development of microalbuminuria. Microalbuminuria is characterized by abnormally low levels of albumin in the urine (9,10).

There is no study that has been discovered in the body of published research that demonstrates the connection between 24-hour urine LPC 2 levels and laboratory and clinical indicators in obese children who are still in the childhood age group. As a result, the purpose of this research was to evaluate the association between 24-hour urine LPC 2 levels and laboratory and clinical indicators in children who are obese.

2.GENERAL INFORMATION

2.1. Obesity

2.1.1. Definition of Obesity:

According to Ylmaz (1999), the term "obesity" refers to obesity, "obese" refers to someone who is excessively fat, and "overweight" refers to someone who has a weight that is excessive for their height and build. The term obesity originated in Latin, where it was translated as "obese." The term "obese" may be used interchangeably with "fat" and "well-nourished" (Durukan, 2001).

The accumulation of an unhealthy quantity of fat in the body is one definition of obesity. The body mass index (BMI), which is calculated by dividing an individual's weight by their height in square meters (kg/m^2), is the metric that is used in clinical settings to characterize obesity. Children are overweight if their body mass index (BMI) falls between the 85th and 95th percentiles on the BMI percentile curves that have been developed according to age and gender. Obese children have a BMI that is above the 95th percentile (4,5).

2.1.2. Prevalence of Obesity:

The incidence of obesity is growing at an alarming rate across all age groups today. This is due to the excessive intake of fats and carbs that is associated with the dietary habits brought about by contemporary living, as well as the fact that children are turning away from active play in favor of engaging in activities like as watching television and playing video games (1,2).

The risk of childhood obesity begins to rise in the child's first year of life and continues to rise between the ages of 5 and 6 until puberty. One in three obese youngsters and eighty percent of obese teenagers will carry their excess weight into adulthood. On the other hand, it is well established that the origin of obesity in adulthood may be traced back to childhood in around thirty percent of cases. Babies who are born with a low or high birth weight have a higher likelihood of becoming fat as children and as adults (11).

The National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), which is regularly conducted in the United States of America, is a reputable source of data on the country's obesity rate. According to the findings of the NHANES III screening that took place between 1988 and 1994, 13.7% of children aged 6-11 years old have a body mass index that is greater than the

95th percentile; this number is 14.7% for boys and 12.5% for girls. Between the ages of 12-17, the proportion of children with a BMI that is greater than the 95th percentile is 11.5% (12.3% for boys and 12.5% for girls) (12). According to the most recent NHANES survey, conducted in 2007-2008, the percentage of boys aged 6-11 years old who had a body mass index (BMI) that was greater than the 95th percentile was 21.2%, while the percentage of girls was 18%. The percentage of boys aged 12-19 years old who had a BMI greater than the 95th percentile was 19.3%, while the percentage of girls was 16.8%. (13). During the years 1994 and 2007, there was a rise of 44% in the frequency of obesity among children aged 6 to 11, and there was a rise of 56% among adolescents aged 12 to 19.

Due to methodological issues in the definition of obesity and insufficient data to reflect the demographic, cultural, and socioeconomic composition of the population, studies on the prevalence of childhood obesity and the increasing trend of childhood obesity in the countries of the European Union (EU) have not been fully concluded. This is because of the increasing trend of childhood obesity. On the other hand, the prevalence of obesity in adolescents is lower in EU nations in early children than it is in adolescents. There is no national research that investigates the prevalence of obesity in our country; nevertheless, there are studies conducted at the regional level. It has been claimed that the prevalence of childhood obesity in our nation has climbed from 6-7 percent to 15-16 percent in the previous 20 years (14). Both 9.1% and 12.8% of youngsters in our nation were found to have a prevalence of obesity in two separate field investigations that were conducted here. The prevalence of obesity was found to be 7.5% in the large field survey conducted by Cinaz et al. that included 12600 school students between the ages of 6 and 14, while the prevalence of children with excessive weight was found to be 6.3%, for a total prevalence of 13.8%. (15,16).

There is a correlation between the amount of socioeconomic deprivation and the prevalence of obesity. It has been shown that greater sociocultural levels in industrialized nations are associated with a higher prevalence of obesity.

2.1.3. Classification of Obesity: .

Obesity.

1. According to the distribution and anatomical features of the adipose tissue,

2. It can be divided according to the factors that play a role in the etiology.
3. Obesity can be classified in several ways, according to the age of onset.

1. Obesity according to the distribution and anatomical features of adipose tissue :

During 24 weeks of pregnancy, adipose tissue may be seen in the fetus, and after 30 weeks, its development speeds up significantly. The nutritional quality of the mother and the length of gestation both influence the amount of adipose tissue that is present in the newborn infant. The quantity of lipid, as well as the number of fat cells and their content, begins to rise throughout the first year of a person's existence. A healthy newborn infant will have 14% of their body weight made up of adipose tissue. Its rate skyrockets throughout childhood and peaks between the ages of 9 and 18, a month-to-month rise of up to 28 percent. In males who are 10 years old, adipose tissue makes up 23% of their total weight, whereas in girls it makes up 28%. This percentage drops to 12% in males by the age of 18, whereas it hovers around 25% in girls throughout this age range. It has been shown that obesity may begin as early as infancy, that obese infants have larger fat cell sizes and a greater number of fat cells overall than children of normal weight. If obesity is a problem that develops throughout childhood or adolescence, the number of fat cells in the body might rise by three to five times the usual amount (17).

a. Hypercellular obesity : It is obesity with an increase in the number of fat cells and is a type of obesity in childhood. Rarely, it can occur in adulthood.

b. Hypertrophic obesity : It is characterized by an increase in the size and lipid content of fat cells. Obesity that starts in adulthood and pregnancy is of this type.

c. Obesity according to fat distribution : Abdominal obesity poses a risk for the development of insulin resistance, cardiovascular disease, non-insulin-dependent diabetes, and cerebrovascular accident in adults. Fat distribution in humans differs from person to person. Especially in men, more abdominal fat is collected, and this appearance is called male type or android type fat distribution. In women, it tends to accumulate more in the gluteal region, and the accumulation of fat in the hips and abdomen is called gynecoid obesity, lower body obesity or pear type obesity.

2. According to etiology:

- a. Simple Obesity (Exogenous Obesity)
- b. Obesity secondary to metabolic and hormonal disorders
 - I. endocrine causes
 1. Hypothalamic disorders
 - a. Frohlich Syndrome
 - b. Trauma
 - c. Tumor (Craniopharyngioma)
 - D. Post-infectious (Encephalitis)
 2. Cushing's Disease and Syndrome
 3. Hypothyroidism
 4. Growth hormone deficiency
 5. Pseudohypoparathyroidism
 6. Insulinoma, Hyperinsulinism
 7. Polycystic Ovary Syndrome
 - ii. Medicines
 1. Glucocorticoids
 2. Amitriptyline (Tricyclic antidepressants)
 3. Cyproheptadine
 4. Phenothiazine
 5. Estrogen
 6. Progesterone

7. Lithium

c. Obesity with genetic syndromes

I. Prader-Willi Syndrome

ii. Bardet-Biedl Syndrome

iii. Cohen Syndrome

iv. Carpenter Syndrome

v. Turner Syndrome

vi. Alström's Syndrome (18,19)

3. Evaluation by Obesity Onset Age:

Although obesity develops in all age groups, its prevalence is higher in the ages when physiologically rapid fat deposition occurs (18).

According to the age of onset of obesity.

- *Childhood onset obesity*
- *Adult-onset obesity*

2.1.4. Etiopathogenesis of Obesity:

The imbalance that develops when a person's energy intake exceeds their energy expenditure ultimately results in obesity. This imbalance tips the scales in favor of energy consumption. During childhood and adolescence, the process of thermogenesis, which is the body's natural process for producing heat, as well as growth, require the utilization of the energy that is gained from the consumption of food. This energy is also required for the maintenance of the body's basal metabolic balance. The varied roles played by hereditary and environmental variables, which impact all these components, contribute to the development of obesity (20).

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The hypothalamus oversees maintaining a healthy weight and energy level in the body. Food intake may be stimulated by stimulating the lateral hypothalamic (LHA) nucleus of the hypothalamus, but it can be inhibited by stimulating the ventromedial hypothalamic (VMH) nucleus of the hypothalamus. Anorexia is the result of injury to the LHA, whereas hyperphagia and obesity are the results of damage to the VMH. The maintenance of an appropriate energy balance is influenced by a wide variety of neurotransmitters, hormones, and other biological substances.

Catecholamines (Epinephrine-Norepinephrine): They function as inhibitors of insulin. They increase glucose from the liver, glycogenolysis in liver and muscle, and lactate release from muscle.

Corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF): It is anorexigenic. Leptin increases CRF synthesis (21).

Urocortin: homologous to CRF and inhibits food intake. This effect is higher than CRF (21).

Cholecystokinin: It is released from the duodenum during feeding, inhibits food intake by providing a feeling of satiety (21).

Glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1): It is an anorexigenic peptide synthesized in the gut and brain. Intraventricular administration inhibits food intake (21).

Serotonin (5-Hydroxytryptamine,5-HT): . Following the injection of noradrenaline and adrenaline into the hypothalamus, food intake is stimulated, while 5-HT injection inhibits food intake (21,22).

Leptin: The leptin gene is responsible for its synthesis in adipose tissue. It does its work by connecting to receptors in the leptomeninges, choroid plexus, and hypothalamus, and it does this by transporting its active system across the blood-brain barrier. Leptin reduces the amount of food that a person consumes, but it also causes an increase in the amount of energy that is

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expended by the body and a reduction in the amount of adipose tissue. The elevated level of leptin that is seen in obese persons is thought to be the consequence of leptin resistance as well as enhanced production in adipose tissue. This is the theory behind the phenomenon. Insulin, glucocorticoids, and estrogen all contribute to an increase in the amount of leptin that is produced in adipose tissue. The action of leptin on the beta cells of the pancreas prevents insulin from being secreted. The development of leptin resistance in pancreatic cells results in a lack of the inhibitory impact that leptin normally has on insulin production, which in turn leads to hyperinsulinemia. In the research that has been done on the subject, obesity caused by a lack of leptin at birth has been documented (21).

Insulin: It is the principal regulator hormone involved in the process of maintaining energy homeostasis. It promotes the intake of energy substrates, storage of those substrates, and protein synthesis. It does this by stimulating the production of glycogen, increasing the breakdown of triglycerides, and stimulating the absorption of free fatty acids by tissues. Because of this, it brings down the amount of circulating lipids and makes room for the storage of more calories. Leptin production is stimulated as a result. If persons with insulin resistance do not experience this impact, it is possible that they will become obese (21).

Opioids: The POMC precursor polypeptide is encoded by the gene known as POMC. This precursor polypeptide eventually gives rise to the peptides ACTH and -MSH, both of which are not opioids. -Endorphin is an opioid. Opioids are orexigenic signals. The most important ones are called enkephalins, beta-endorphins, and dynorphins (21).

Neuropeptide Y (NPY): It belongs to the family of hormones known as pancreatic polypeptides. It has been shown that the expression of NPY-mRNA is elevated during periods of fasting, particularly in neurons that reach all the way to arcuate and paraventricular nuclei. It has been shown that injecting NPY into the ventricle and some regions of the brain will increase the amount of food consumed, and it has been hypothesized that NPY is released as a natural physiological reaction to feelings of hunger.

CART: Originates from the arcuate nucleus. While its expression decreases during fasting, it increases when leptin is given (21).

Galanin: Increases appetite. The proximity of the synthesis region in the brain with NPY suggests that nutritional induction due to NPY is regulated by galanin (23,24).

Melanin concentrating hormone (MCH): Orexigenic. MCH genes in the hypothalamus are expressed during fasting.

Melanocortin receptors and AGRP: Melanocortins are part of the larger category of hormones known as melanocortins, which also includes AGRP and α -MSH. The MC4R and MC3R melanocortin receptors are the ones that participate in the control of one's body weight. When α -MSH binds to MC4R, it creates a sense of fullness in the body. It is believed that melanocortins, MSH, and AGRP are the pathways by which leptin's metabolic actions are mediated.

The human counterpart of the agouti protein is referred to as AGRP (agouti related protein). When α -MSH is prevented from binding to MC4R when AGRP is present, obesity, hyperinsulinemia, and hyperglycemia are the results. MC4R mutations are the most prevalent kind of inherited abnormality seen in obese persons (22).

Ghrelin: It does this by turning on NPY and AGRP, which leads to an increase in both calorie intake and fat accumulation. The hormone ghrelin is secreted at higher levels during fasting and at lower levels after a meal. Ghrelin levels have been discovered to be abnormally low in obese people, although it has been demonstrated that these levels may revert to normal if the patient loses weight (25,26).

Interleukin 6 (IL-6) and Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α): They stop the process of lipogenesis while stimulating lipolysis. They contribute to the destruction of adipocytes. As a result, they have an impact that is anti-obesity. TNF- α plays a significant role in the development of insulin resistance in obesity, and there is a connection between obesity and the production of C-reactive protein, which is triggered by IL-6 (3).

Adiponectin: It has an anti-inflammatory and preventative action against atherosclerosis. In obese people, adiponectin levels were found to be significantly lower. There is a strong correlation between this low level and insulin resistance (21).

Table: 1 - Biological molecules involved in the regulation of food intake

Factors That Reduce Food Intake:

Neurotransmitters:

Norepinephrine-B Receptor

Dopamine

Serotonin

Hypothalamic Peptides:

Corticotropin-Releasing Factor (CRF)

Urocortin

Glucagon-Like Peptide 1 (GLP-1)

Cholecystokinin (CCK)

Peripheral Factors:

Leptin-Long-Acting Signal

Cholecystokinin (CCK) Food-Related Signal

Insulin

Factors That Increase Food Intake:

Central Factors:

Norepinephrine-A Receptor

Neuropeptide Y (NPY)

Melanin Concentrating Hormone (MCH)

Galanin

Growth Hormone-Releasing Hormone (GHRH)

Opioid Peptides

Peripheral Factors:

Hypoglycemia

2.1.5. Risk Factors Affecting Obesity:

1. DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS

1.a.) Age : It has been shown that there are times in a child's life when they are more susceptible to becoming obese. The second six months of the first age are the first critical danger period, the second risk period is between the ages of 4 and 6, and the third risk period is the pubertal phase. Obesity that develops in a kid during the second half of their first year of life is significant in terms of the likelihood of developing obesity in the years to come. The amount of fat tissue in the body reaches its lowest point between the ages of 6 and 8 years old, after which it begins to gradually rise once again. The adolescent years are the third potential source of loss. Currently, females have an increase in their adipose tissue, whilst boys experience a reduction. On the other hand, whereas adipose tissue tends to be more prevalent in girls' hips, it is more often seen in males' midsections. The risk of developing cardiovascular disease, hyperlipidemia, glucose intolerance, and hypertension increases with increasing levels of body fat. The morbidity issues that were brought on by obesity were found at greater rates in teenage females than they were in boys. It has been shown that female and male teenagers who are fat have a greater risk of developing morbidity in adulthood than adolescents who are not obese (27).

1.b.) Gender : It has been shown that the incidence rate is much greater in females as compared to males. Unfortunately, the circumstances of this matter are not the same in every nation. For instance, the incidence is greater in boys in Italy and Austria, even though it is more prevalent in females in England, the United States of America, Spain, and Finland (27).

2. PHYSICAL FACTORS _ _

2.a.) Region : The importance of environmental variables is vitally significant in the prevention of obesity in children, just as it is in adult obesity. For instance, research from the United States' National Health Examination Survey (NHES) indicates that the northeastern part of the country has the highest prevalence of obesity (28).

2.b.) Season : The months of fall and winter seem to be associated with a rise in the incidence of obesity. Although some researchers have attempted to attribute this difference to a decrease in the amount of food consumed with the decrease in air temperature and to a decrease in the

number of sport-related activities, the lower prevalence of obesity in the northern countries in general has put a question mark on the accuracy of this hypothesis. In other words, the lower prevalence of obesity in the northern countries has put a question mark on the accuracy of this hypothesis (28).

2.c.) Settlement : It was shown that populated settlements and towns have a greater frequency of obesity than rural places do. [Citation needed] (29).

3. SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS

3.a.) Socioeconomic status of the family: Much research has been conducted to study the possible link between a family's socioeconomic status and the prevalence of childhood obesity; however, none of these investigations have produced conclusive findings. The NHANES research conducted in the United States was unable to establish an association between the two variables, although the regional investigations discovered the existence of an inverse ratio (28).

Education level of parents: There is a lack of clarity on the link between the education level of parents and the prevalence of obesity. An inverse association was discovered in some of the investigations, but the existence of a meaningful connection was unable to be shown in another group of the research (28).

4. BIOLOGICAL FACTORS

4.a.) Family history : Family history of obesity and excess weight at puberty are the two most crucial factors that determine an individual's adult body weight, as shown by the findings of Mossberg's research, which included the observation of 500 children for nearly 40 years (30).

It has been shown that the existence of an obesity-related family history raises the risk of childhood obesity by roughly three times. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] According to the findings of the research conducted by Vohr et al., it was discovered that one of the parents was fat in 80% of the cases of children who were obese, and both parents were obese in 30% of the cases (31).

4.b.) Birth weight : Birth weight was shown to be a predisposing factor for obesity in children when they were 5 years old by Locard et al. On the other hand, low-birth-weight babies are more likely to develop obesity in infancy and obesity later in life owing to excessive growth

sputrs during the first two years of life. It has been shown that cardiovascular problems may arise (32).

5. HABITS

5. a.) Nutrition: It is also believed that poor nutrition in childhood contributes to obesity later in life. The incidence of obesity is much greater in children who are fed with baby formula rather than being breastfed. Children who consume breast milk between the ages of three and six months had a 35% lower risk of becoming obese compared to children who do not consume breast milk, as shown in a research conducted by von Kries et al (33).

The shift in eating patterns that has been seen is one of the significant repercussions brought on by the quick growth in obesity. A little less than half of the youngsters who live in the city go somewhere else to have their midday meal. Most of them have no choice but to consume "fast food."

It has been discovered in a substantial number of research conducted in Europe that obese youngsters consume an excessive amount of fat and protein derived from animal sources. Since fats have a low thermogenic impact, it has also been shown that there is an almost perfect link between the fat ratio in the diet and the fat ratio in the body. The reason for this is that fats tend to be stored as fat in the body. The process of thermogenesis requires 3% of the lipids that are taken orally, 8% of the proteins, and 25% of the carbs.

Additionally, it has been discovered that the ingested proteins lead to an increase in the storage of fat as well as the proliferation of mature adipocytes through an increase in Insulin-Like Growth Factor-1 (IGF-1) and insulin. This was discovered after it was found that the proteins cause these effects. In addition to that, the number of meals is an essential factor to consider while evaluating obesity. When the number of meals eaten each day decreases, a rise in blood lipid and insulin levels might be expected (28).

A considerable number of youngsters do not have breakfast at home and instead buy a snack from the vending machine in the school cafeteria. These foods are a category; Because of its high caloric value, high fat to carbohydrate ratio, and low fiber and fiber content, it contributes

to the development of obesity and makes it easier to become obese. Consuming foods that are rich in carbohydrate content causes plasma insulin levels to rise, which in turn causes insulin-dependent lipogenesis and, ultimately, an increase in the amount of fat stored in the body.

5. b.) Physical activity : There have not been nearly enough longterm studies done on people's levels of physical activity to determine whether they're using the right methodologies to assess it, despite the fact that a lack of physical activity is thought to be one of the most significant contributors to obesity. In accordance with the findings of previous research, it has been noted, for a variety of reasons, that fat children in the age range of youngsters have an increased propensity to live sedentary lifestyles, comparable to those of adults.

It has been demonstrated that living in multi-story homes in the city, an inadequate supply of playgrounds, an increase in the amount of information load and homework assigned in schools, preparation for selection exams, watching television, and using computers all limit the amount of movement that children are able to engage in.

5. c.) Time of watching television : Children are susceptible to a diverse range of influences due to the pervasive presence of the medium that is television in modern life.

According to the findings of a research conducted in the United States by Roberts et al., the percentage of children in different age groups who spend time in front of the television varies, but it is present in 32% of children aged 2-7, 65% of children aged 8-13, and 65% of teenagers aged 14-18. It became out that there was a television in the room when it was investigated (33).

After this, the American Academy of Pediatrics issued a statement that was intended for parental audiences as well as physicians (23).

An attempt has been made to explain the association between the rise in the amount of time spent in front of the television and the growth in the prevalence of obesity by associating the following variables. A decrease in the amount of energy that is expended while watching television is caused by an increase in the frequency of snacking as well as an increase in the urge to consume high-calorie meals that is indirectly offered by commercials seen on television. On the other hand, given that the same television networks usually take the stance that "weak person is lovely," they also carry with them a feeling of encouragement against weakness (33,34).

It is well known that a drop of 12-15% in overall energy expenditure is associated with an increase of 7.5-10% in body weight. On the other hand, the cause-and-effect link between being overweight and engaging in less physical exercise is not yet completely understood in its entirety. In other words, it is not yet known whether individuals who are obese engage in less physical activity because they are fat, or if people who engage in less physical activity because they are obese (34).

2.1.6. Measurement methods of obesity:

There are direct and indirect methods used to measure body fat:

2.1.6.1. Direct measurement of body fat:

These techniques are based on the measurement of body components that make up the body composition other than adipose tissue and adipose tissue.

- 1) **Underwater body densitometry:** The method known as water body densitometry, which is based on the underwater weighing of several types of tissue (such as lean tissue and adipose tissue) of varying densities, is regarded as the "gold standard." It is quite challenging to administer to youngsters (15).
- 2) **Determination of total body water by isotope dilution:** The calculation is performed by assuming that the percentage of water found in the mass of lean tissue is always the same (72%). (15). The isotope dilution technique, which utilizes either two or three valent hydrogen isotopes, may be used to calculate total body fluid.
- 3) **Measurement of total body potassium:** The measurement of potassium in the body provides information on the mass of lean tissue (15).
- 4) **Measurement of dual energy x-ray absorption (DEXA):** It is favored due to the minimal amount of radiation it emits and the ease with which it may be applied (15).

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5) **Determination of the bioelectrical conductivity of the body:** It is predicated on the disparity in the electrical permeability of the liquid compartment in the electromagnetic field and the adipose tissue. The price is quite steep (15).

6) **Neutron activation:** Because of the large amount of radiation required, its use is restricted. The quantity of calcium that is found in the bones is regarded to be constant, as is the nitrogen-to-protein ratio in the structure of the protein, and the body's protein and nitrogen levels are calculated (15).

7) **Display methods:** USG, CT, and MRI all provide some insight into the regional distribution of fat.

2.1.6.2. Indirect measurement of body fat (Anthropometric measurements):

Since they are simple, straightforward, useful, and not too costly, anthropometric measures are widely used in the process of diagnosing obesity. They include the body mass index, circumference measures, skinfold thicknesses, and weight for height, often known as relative weight (Quetelet index).

1) **Weight for height (Relative weight):** It is the standard diagnostic criteria that is used when attempting to establish whether a kid is overweight. Using the tables that include height and weight values that are organized according to age and gender, one may determine the weight (ideal weight) that a kid should have according to their height age (the age at which the height is in the 50th percentile). Weight in comparison: The weight of the patient is determined by multiplying their actual weight by 100 and dividing it by their optimum weight. Overweight is defined as having a relative weight that is between 110 and 120% of one's ideal weight, while obesity is defined as having a relative weight that is more than 120%. (35).

2) **Body Mass Index (BMI) (Body Mass Index-BMI) (Quetelet Index):** It is thought to be the indicator that most accurately represents the makeup of the body. Weight in kilograms divided by height is the formula that is used to determine it (m²). Between the 85th and 95th percentile is overweight, and anything over the 95th percentile is obese, according to boundaries that are established by age and gender (36).

- 3) **Skinfold thickness:** The assessment of skinfold thickness is a useful diagnostic criteria because obesity results in the accumulation of most of the the body's extra fat beneath the skin. Using a caliper, it is measured from the triceps, the biceps, the supscapular, and the suprailiac areas, and then it is graded using tables that were produced according to gender and age (37).
- 4) **Waist Circumference/Hip Circumference Ratio:** These are indirect measures that reveal how much fat is concentrated in the abdominal region. Adults have an increased risk of cardiovascular disease if their score is more than 0.9, while children have an increased risk of insulin resistance and dyslipidemia if their value is larger than 0.8. (38).
- 5) **Circumference measurements:** It is an indication of body density, total body protein mass, adipose tissue mass, and total body lean body mass. Moreover, it might reveal energy storage. The most popular circumferences to employ are those of the upper and middle arm, waist, hips, thighs, and calves.

2.1.7. Complications of Obesity:

Obesity is in and of itself a risk factor that may lead to the development of morbidity and death. This condition affects a person's psychosocial state in addition to the endocrine system, cardiovascular system, respiratory system, gastrointestinal system, skin, genitourinary system, and musculoskeletal system. The rates at which these systems are impacted by this disease vary. The consequences of obesity become apparent sooner and more often the longer a person has the condition and the more severe it becomes.

a) **Cardiovascular Complications:**

The chance of developing cardiovascular disease is significantly increased when obese individuals are present (39). Recent research has shown that smoking, dyslipidemia, hypertension, reduced exercise, and obesity are substantial risk factors for cardiovascular disease in children and adolescents. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] (40). When obesity is established and maintained from infancy, it increases the likelihood of developing cardiovascular disease later in life (41).

Atherosclerosis is caused by cholesterol building up in the artery wall, which is made worse by elevated levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL), triacylglycerol (TG), and cholesterol. By removing cholesterol from the body's peripheral tissues and delivering it to the liver, HDL plays

a significant part in the process of preventing atherosclerosis. Diet and exercise are the primary tools used in the treatment of obesity, with the goals of lowering LDL and cholesterol levels and raising HDL levels.

It is estimated that between 20 and 30 percent of obese children between the ages of 5 and 11 years old have elevated systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Half of all instances of hypertension in children and adolescents are caused by obesity. It has been discovered that the body weight, BMI, skinfold thickness, and hip circumference of persons who had hypertension in childhood and continued to have hypertension in adulthood were greater than those of those who did not continue to have hypertension into adulthood (42).

b) Respiratory System Complications:

The most significant impact that obesity has on a person's ability to breathe is an increase in residual volume, which occurs as a direct consequence of an increase in abdominal pressure above the diaphragm (43). The requirements for respiratory effort, oxygen consumption, and the elimination of carbon dioxide increased in obese individuals. Pickwick Syndrome, also known as Obesity Hypoventilation Syndrome, is brought on by a reduction in the amount of carbon dioxide that is excreted. This leads to hypoxemia and hypercapnia. The recurrent stopping of air flow during sleep because of a collapse in the upper airways is the hallmark symptom of obstructive sleep apnea. The association between obesity and sleep apnea may be explained by the greater neck circumference that occurs in patients who have sleep apnea (44,45).

c) Gastrointestinal System Complications:

Cholelithiasis is the predominant symptom of obesity in the hepatobiliary system. Obesity may also cause other symptoms. The development of steatosis in the liver is linked to elevated levels of VLDL synthesis, which is caused by hyperinsulinemia. Twenty to twenty-five percent of children who are obese exhibit symptoms of steatohepatitis, such as elevated levels of transaminases or ultrasonographic abnormalities. There is a correlation between the severity and length of obesity as well as the gender of the patient when it comes to the advancement of steatohepatitis to fibrosis (46).

d) Endocrinological Complications:

Insulin resistance is the key pathophysiological mechanism underlying the association between obesity and type 2 diabetes. The existence of hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance in obese people raises the chance of acquiring type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, hyperlipidemia, and hypertension in later life. Obese people also have a higher risk of having hyperlipidemia. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) (47,48) established the following criteria for the diagnosis of metabolic syndrome in children and adolescents in the year 2007:

6-10 years: A waist circumference that is more than the 90th percentile indicates obesity.

Between the ages of 10 to 16, respectively: Obesity defined as having a waist circumference that is more than the 90th percentile (or, if lower, using the adult limitations), in addition to at least two of the following criteria:

Triglyceride > 150 mg/dL (1.7 mmol/L)

HDL < 40 mg/dL (103 mmol/L).

Systolic blood pressure more than 130 mm/Hg and diastolic blood pressure greater than 85 mm/Hg

glucose levels higher than 100 mg/dL (5.6 mmol/L) (OGTT is necessary) or a diagnosed case of type 2 diabetes

Adult standards are applied to those who are older than 16 years old.

The presence of two of the following four criteria, in addition to central obesity, is required to make a diagnosis of metabolic syndrome.

1. Triglyceride > 150 mg/dL or receiving treatment for lipid elevation
2. HDL < 40 mg/dL in men and < 50 mg/dL in women, or being treated for this lipid abnormality
3. Blood pressure systolic > 130 mm/Hg diastolic > 85 mm/Hg or previously receiving treatment for hypertension
4. High fasting blood glucose (> 100 mg/dL) or previously diagnosed type 2 DM

Women who are obese have an increased risk of experiencing menstrual irregularities. When a woman achieves an average body weight of 31 kilos and a body fat percentage of 22 percent, menstruation often starts. For this reason, early puberty may occur in females who are fat. Obesity has been linked to both oligomenorrhea and amenorrhea in certain cases. Oligomenorrhea and amenorrhea are both symptoms of polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), which is also characterized by obesity, insulin resistance, hirsutism, acne, and acanthosis

nigricans. Between forty and sixty percent of females who have polycystic ovarian syndrome are overweight (44).

To maintain a normal level of cortisol, the production of adrenal cortisol is stimulated by an ACTH stimulation. This is done to compensate for the degradation of cortisol. The buildup of belly fat, a rise in the synthesis of adrenal sex hormones (DHEA and testosterone), and early onset of adrenarche are the typical outcomes of an elevated ACTH level in obese individuals (49).

Androgen production is enhanced in persons who are obese due to increased activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal and adrenal axis, as well as the stimulation of ovarian and adrenal androgen production caused by hyperinsulinemia. In addition to this, the process by which androgens are converted into estrogen is sped up. Growing usage of sex steroids has been linked to advanced bone age and earlier onset of puberty (21).

D) Psychological Complications:

Children who are obese almost always suffer from mental strain. It has been shown that psychological problems associated to distorted body image, such as sadness, loss of self-esteem, being disliked by others, and feeling loathed, are more frequent in obese teenagers than they are in adolescents who are not fat. These disorders include: (50).

E) Neurological Complications:

Obesity is associated with an increase in intra-abdominal pressure, which leads to an increase in pleural and ventricular filling pressure. This, in turn, generates idiopathic intracranial hypertension owing to the presence of counter-resistance in the cerebral veins. It has been shown that people who suffer from idiopathic intracranial hypertension are much more likely to be fat. Those who had a body weight that was more than 10% over their target weight were 14 times more likely to develop idiopathic intracranial hypertension, and those who had a body weight that was more than 20% above their ideal weight were 20 times more likely to develop the condition (44).

F) Nephrological Complications

Insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes are both conditions that may be caused by obesity, which is a well-known risk factor. In addition, unlike diabetes, obesity is linked to glomerular

hyperfiltration, the development of glomerulosclerosis, and kidney failure. All these conditions may occur on their own. It has been observed that renal endothelial dysfunction and increased renin-angiotensin system activity have a role in the development of microalbuminuria. Microalbuminuria is characterized by abnormally low levels of albumin in the urine (9,10).

In addition, several research have shown a favorable association between body mass index and microalbuminuria (59,60). A significant positive connection was found between body mass index and microalbuminuria in both men and women in the Gubbio population research that was conducted in Italy (60).

2.1.8. Insulin Resistance in Obesity:

Obesity occurs because of an increase in triglyceride storage in adipose tissue, and because of this increase, the responsiveness of muscle and adipose tissue to insulin declines. There is a decrease in the insulin-induced glucose transfer. It is hypothesized that fatty acids participate in the occurrence of this phenomena (51). When the level of fatty acids in the plasma rises, the insulin sensitivity of the liver, muscle, and fat cells all decreases. It has been hypothesized that the downregulation of this gene was caused by either a reduction in the total number of insulin receptors or an expansion of the cell membrane surfaces. While treating diabetes type 2, the objective is to lower insulin resistance as much as possible. Antidiabetic medications taken orally are utilized in the therapy, although they have been linked to increased adipocyte differentiation, which may lead to weight gain (51,52). One school of thought contends that insulin resistance is a kind of adaptive mechanism that stops one from gaining any more weight. Adipose tissue will continue to expand while there is a positive energy balance, and this will continue to be the case until insulin resistance develops. Because insulin resistance decreases the accumulation of triglycerides that happens when insulin is present. In this context, insulin resistance is the adaptation that should be aimed for since it will lessen the impact of obesity.

2.1.8.1. *Insulin resistance measurement methods:*

1. **Indirect Methods:**

a. Fasting insulin level: Routine use is not recommended because it gives comparable results between normal and insulin resistant individuals and there is no standardization (53).

b. Insulin, glucose, and C-peptide ratios:

- Insulin (pM) /glycemia (pM) >22
- Glucose (mg/dl) /insulin (μ U/ml) <6
- Insulin (pM) / C-peptide (pM) >0.1 indicates insulin resistance.

c. 1st hour insulin level in OGTT: Insulin level > 150 μ U/ml at 1 hour in OGTT indicates insulin resistance.

2. Direct Methods:

a. Hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic insulin clamp technique: It is accepted as the gold standard method. However, it is not preferred because it is expensive and time consuming and does not show β -cell sensitivity.

b. HOMA-IR (Homeostasis Model Assesment-Insulin Resistance): It is an easily applicable test that shows both insulin resistance and β -cell function.

$$\text{HOMA-IR} = \text{Fasting insulin level}(\mu\text{U/ml}) \times \text{Fasting glucose}(\text{mg/dl}) / 450$$

c. Continuous infusion model of glucose (CIGMA): It provides information about insulin resistance, β -cell function, and glucose intolerance.

d. Minimal model (frequent IVGTT): It is a test that can detect glucose sensitivity with glucose and insulin values obtained from intravenous glucose tolerance test.

Treatment in Childhood Obesity:

Childhood obesity is divided into two groups according to its etiopathogenesis and their treatment is arranged according to these groups (54).

1-Primary Obesity; It is formed by the effect of genetic and environmental factors. The treatment is examined under four main headings.

Ensuring nutritional balance

Increasing exercise and daily activity

Pharmacological treatment

Surgical treatment

According to studies, after nine years, eighty percent of obese children who successfully reduce weight would be back to where they were in terms of their weight percentile. Because of this, the therapy for obesity should take the form of a multidisciplinary treatment that involves education, food, activity, exercise, and lifestyle modification. Moreover, the engagement of the patient's family should be encouraged throughout the process. Patients and their families should be taught about how to apply dietary guidelines to everyday life, and they should be informed about the calorie content of foods, the contents of those items, and the food exchange schedules.

2-Secondary Obesity is characterized by the development of hypothalamic, neurological, psychological, endocrine, and chromosomal abnormalities because of skeletal dysplasias and long-term pharmaceutical use. It is feasible to treat the condition by addressing the underlying reasons.

Providing Nutritional Balance and Regulation of Nutrition

The fact that children are living creatures who are always expanding, and maturing is the single most significant distinction between them and adults. Because of this, it is not suitable to offer extremely limited diets to children in the same way that adults do. The nutrition plan that will be provided should include adequate calories and critical components to promote proper growth and development, as well as a balanced quantity of protein, carbohydrates, and fat (55).

When it comes to youngsters who are fed with an extremely high quantity of high calories, moving abruptly to a diet that is low in calories will diminish the likelihood of the diet being successful. In this scenario, the most effective method would be for the dietitian to collect the child's dietary history over the course of seven to eight days to calculate the child's typical calorie consumption over the course of a day. As a starting point, the average number of calories is calculated, and then that number is decreased by 10–20% at regular intervals of 6–8 weeks, until the optimal number of calories that should be consumed daily is reached. The standard number of calories that should be provided to children who are obese may be cut down to 80%

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of the standard number of calories that should be taken according to the optimum weight, and it can even be lowered to 60% for a brief period in children who are seriously fat. Carbohydrates should account for 50% of the daily calorie intake that is provided, while fats should provide 30%, and proteins should provide 20%. Within the realm of carbs, complex carbohydrates should be favored, whereas within the realm of fats, unsaturated fats should take precedence. In a healthy diet, there should be an even distribution of proteins derived from both plants and animals. It should have an enough quantity of the trace components. Diets that induce quick weight reduction in the short term, but do so at the expense of these rates, are hazardous to one's health and are of no benefit since they cannot be maintained over the long run. A negative nitrogen balance is caused by low-calorie diets, which in turn causes a loss of lean body mass and other adverse effects that are not physiological in nature.

The quantity of cholesterol that is consumed in one day's worth of food should not be more than 300 milligrams, and the recommended range for that amount is between 100 and 150 milligrams. It is important to include foods high in fiber into one's diet, not only to cut down on the total number of calories consumed but also to postpone the onset of feelings of hunger owing to the slower rate at which fiber is absorbed and digested. The recommended daily intake of fiber should be between 20 and 30 mg. Fresh vegetables, fruits, and legumes are the three most common sources of pulpy foods (54,56).

While making dietary adjustments, it is important to take into consideration the glycemic index of the items that are consumed. It has been established that increased food intake is caused by metabolic and hormonal changes that take place following the consumption of meals with a high glycemic index. [Citation needed] [Citation needed]

The incidence of obesity is much higher in babies who are given baby formula as opposed to those who are breastfed. Thus, nursing at home is the method that should be prioritized. The infant must be fed about every three hours, and no extra foods should be introduced until the baby is at least four months old. Stop giving your child milk from a bottle as soon as you possibly can (55,56).

For infants who must be fed formula food, the formula should be prepared in the amount and concentration that is appropriate for their age. Additionally, foods like sugar, honey, biscuits, and cornflakes should not be added to the prepared foods. For babies who must be breastfed,

the formula should be prepared in the amount and concentration that is appropriate for their age.

When adding new foods to the diet, custard should be limited to no more than one serving per day, and other meals, such as vegetable soups, yoghurt, vegetable purees, fresh vegetables, and fruits, should be favored (54)

It is important to consume less junk food, which refers to high-calorie meals like candy, chocolate cake, candy, and ready-made fruit drinks. There should be limits placed on the consumption of foods that are referred to be ready meals, such as hamburgers, french fries, doner rolls, pizza, and related items. It is best to refrain from snacking in between meals on foods that are high in calories. It is strongly recommended that people stop eating at fast food restaurants and stay away from meals rich in calories in the hours before going to bed.

Organizing Exercise and Daily Activity

Exercise and regulation of daily activity are an important part of obesity treatment. Successful results are obtained when diet and exercise are combined (55,57).

Positive Effects of Exercise on Obesity

a) Exercise Requires the Use of Calories .

Since exercise increases the use of calories, children should be encouraged to spend their spare time active instead of passive activities.

b) Exercise is Effective in Preventing the Negative Effects of Obesity .

Complications of obesity in adults are metabolic and mechanical. In children, unlike adults, hyperlipidemia, psychosocial factors, hepatic steatosis, and disorders in carbohydrate metabolism are at the forefront. Most importantly, the risk of continuation of existing obesity in adulthood has doubled.

c) Exercise Reduces Lean Body Mass Loss

Twenty-five percent of the weight lost with diet is lean body mass. Loss of lean body mass is minimized with aerobic-style exercises.

d) Exercise Inhibits Metabolic Decline Caused by Diet

Calorie restriction induces a drop-in basal metabolic rate. This discount might go as high as 20% in certain cases. The drop-in basal metabolic rate that occurs because of diet is compensated for by the increase in energy expenditure that occurs because of exercise, and the weight loss that results is certain to be permanent.

It is advised that children who are obese begin their exercise regimen with low-intensity activities that last for a brief period. Thereafter, they should continue to increase the frequency, intensity, and length of their workouts. Activities that the kid will love, such as cycling, dancing, tennis, swimming, volleyball, jumping rope, and so on, should be favored when it comes to the physical activity program for it to be effective (56,57).

During the first 15 to 20 minutes of the workout, you should continue to gradually increase the time spent on the activity until you reach 45 minutes total. Exercise should first be performed three to four times a week, but this number should gradually rise until it is performed each day of the week.

It is recommended that, in addition to the exercise program, an active lifestyle be adopted in order to increase the amount of calories consumed in daily life (not to spend too much time in front of the TV and computer – try to use the stairs instead of the elevator, prefer walking instead of the car for short distances, etc.), and that the family should serve as a model for the child in this regard. In addition, it is recommended that an active lifestyle be adopted to increase the number of calories consumed in daily life.

The presence of sports places that are readily accessible to social support, the coverage of these topics in the media, and socioeconomic circumstances are all important variables in determining what constitutes an active lifestyle and in avoiding obesity. Children who are ill or have disabilities could need programs that are either more specialized or adapted. Further suggestions can be provided for disorders that occur simultaneously.

Pharmacological Treatment

The use of pharmaceuticals in the management of obesity in children and adolescents is not recommended, and most of the research on various pharmacological treatments has been conducted on adult patients. On the other hand, it is anticipated that it will be tried on children who have been found to have morbid obesity and who do not react to traditional therapies. In situations like these, the affected patient is hospitalized in one of the clinic's private rooms, and drug treatment is conducted under careful observation (58). The medications sibutramine, orlistat, ephedrine, and caffeine are the most often utilized (21). When administered to obese youngsters suffering from hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance, metformin proved to be an effective treatment that brought about the desired outcomes.

Surgical treatment.

Criteria Used for Surgical Treatment

- 1 - Massive obesity (more than twice the ideal weight)
- 2 - Presence of massive obesity for at least two years
- 3- Implementation of diet therapy for at least two years and
Determination of disability by clinicians
- 4 - Absence of endocrine and metabolic diseases that may lead to obesity
- 5- Absence of a disease that may increase the risk of operation
- 6- The patient's willingness for treatment after the postoperative side effects and complications are stated.
- 7 - The patient's mental capacity and emotional state should be at a level that can tolerate the changes that may occur during and after the operation.

Gastroplasty and jejunoileal shunt are the most current surgical treatment methods. However, the results of a few rare cases tried in children are not positive (57).

2.2.Lipocalins

Lipocalins are proteins that come in a variety of forms and may be found in bacteria, plants, and mammals. The class of proteins known as lipocalins gained its name from the Greek words for lipos and calyx (35,44). The calcin group is a structural superfamily that includes fatty acid-binding proteins (FABP), avidins, metalloproteinase inhibitors, and lipocalins. Lipocalins are members of the calcin group that make up the structural superfamily.

Even though the amino acid sequences of the members of the lipocalin family are quite different from one another, each of them has a highly conserved motif in their amino acid sequence that is referred to as the short, conserved domain (SCR). These areas have important roles to play functionally, and when combined, they constitute the receptor binding site on the cell surface (35,37). Based on the amount of SCR motifs that are present in a lipocalin, the protein may be classified into one of two subfamilies. Both the Kernel (which is situated within), and Outer Surface Lipocalins are present.

KERNEL LIPOCALINS

1) Retinol binding proteins

Retinol binding proteins are a single polypeptide chain consisting of 182 amino acids and take part in Vitamin A transport, forming a holoprotein complex with transthyretin (thyroid hormone binding protein) (61).

2)B-lacoglobulin

It has 162 amino acids in its monomer form and contains five cystines. It plays a role in facilitating the digestion of milk fats and removing free fatty acids from the environment (62).

3) Chondrogenesis-related lipocalins (CAL)

These lipocalins, Ex-FABP, CAL β and CAL γ , participate in cartilage formation and inflammatory response. They have essential functions in the immune response. They also inhibit cell death (63).

4) Lipocalin type prostaglandin Synthetase (L-PGDS)

It takes part in inflammation and apoptosis. They play a role in induction of sleep, inhibition of platelet aggregation and nitric oxide secretion, and induction of vasodilation (64). Increased expression has been shown in ovarian cancers and is thought to be a marker for cancer progression (65).

5) Apolipoprotein D

It is known that apolipo protein D (Apo D) is effective in cognitive functions and behavioral characteristics of Alzheimer's patients and neuropathy patients. In addition, the amount of Apo-D was found to be increased in the amyloid bodies of those with amyloid angiopathy (66).

OUTLIER LIPOCALINS

They differ from kernel lipocalins only in that they contain a different number of SCRs.

1) Apolipoprotein M

Apo M is an outer lipocalin with 188 amino acids and is found in the structure of HDL. However, it is found to a lesser extent in triglycerides and LDL. It is synthesized in the kidneys and liver. Transgenic mouse experiments suggest that it may have antiatherogenic properties.

2) Odorant Binding Proteins (OBP)

They are found in the nasal mucosa and vomero-nasal mucosa and take part in the transport of odorous molecules, their detoxification (by removing lipid peroxidases). It is thought that they play a role in the recognition of pheromones in vertebrates (66,67).

3) Krustasianin

4) Lipocalin-2(LCN 2)

5) Nitrophorins

It shows anticoagulant effect in insects (68).

6) Histamine binding proteins

7) Violaxanthin de-epoxidase (VDE)

It causes light-dependent cyclic changes of xanthophylls and enables plants to adapt to different lights (66).

8) Bacterial Lipocalins (Blc)

It was first isolated in 1995 from the stable growth phase of E.coli under stress conditions. They are exposed because of membrane damage (69).

2.2.1.Lipocalin-2

(Neutrophil gelatinase Associated Lipocalin (NGAL), (LCN 2), Oncogene24p3, uterocalin, siderocalin)

The structure of LCN 2, which is remarkably like the structures of many other lipocalins, is shaped like a "barrel" and is made up of eight strands of protein. LCN2, which was detected in human neutrophil granules during the early phases of its discovery, was initially identified as neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin when it was discovered (NGAL). This specific protein has a total of 178 residues and a molecular weight of twenty-five kilodaltons in its structure. In addition to the siderophores and small iron-binding molecules that are its principal ligands, the lipocalin family member LCN 2 is capable of binding and transporting hydrophobic lipid molecules as well as other types of hydrophobic molecules. Nevertheless, it is also responsible for the binding of molecules that bind iron (70,71). Its expression is induced by damage to the kidney epithelium and other epithelium (these damages can occur because of infection, inflammation, ischemia, or neoplastic transformation), even though it is expressed at exceptionally low levels in tissues and cells such as the liver, lung, kidney, adipocytes, and macrophages (71,72). According to the findings of studies that were conducted in vitro, LCN 2 is an essential factor in both the apoptotic processes and the survival of cells. In addition to this, it is a crucial factor in the process of encouraging cell differentiation during embryogenesis, which is a process that occurs throughout embryo development (71).

On the surface of the cell, LCN 2 has the potential to bind to two distinct receptors: 24p3R and megalin-kubulin. At least in mice, 24p3R is expressed in most organs; however, the degree of expression in kidney epithelial cells is particularly high. At least in mice, 24p3R is expressed. The synthesis of the megalin-cubulin receptor known as 24p3R, which is highly selective for LCN 2, is the responsibility of the cells that make up the proximal tubule (73).

It has been shown that providing mice with a microgram dosage of LCN 2 provides a high degree of protection against the damage caused by ischemia-reperfusion of the kidneys in mice (acute tubular necrosis). In addition to its role as a protector, it is also a sensitive biomarker that has the potential to provide early warning signs of damage to the kidneys (74,75).

Nicolas et al. With research that was conducted in the year 2008, he was able to show that LCN 2 is an incredibly good biomarker for the early diagnosis of acute renal failure.

2.2.2. Lipocalin 2 and Insulin Resistance

Insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes are both illnesses that have been linked to obesity, which is a well-known risk factor. Insulin resistance is a condition in which the body does not respond normally to insulin. In contrast to diabetes, obesity is associated with glomerular hyperfiltration, the progression of glomerulosclerosis, and kidney failure. There is always the possibility that none of these circumstances may manifest at all. It has been shown that renal endothelial dysfunction and increased activity of the renin-angiotensin system both have a role in the development of microalbuminuria. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] [More citation is required] [More citation is required]

There are now two pathways that are being investigated in connection with insulin resistance. In one of these two mechanisms, the responsibility is attributed to ectopic adipose tissue, but in the other mechanism, the blame is attributed to the endocrine activities of adipose tissue. Both mechanisms have been proposed to explain why obesity occurs (76,77). Insulin resistance syndrome and/or metabolic syndrome are both characterized by high central adiposity, which is one of the primary features of the disorder. Both conditions are associated with an increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes. Rendle's effect is characterized by an increase in the flow of fatty acids and a suppression of insulin action in tissues that are normally sensitive to insulin. This impact is specifically caused by adipose tissue, which is present in visceral storage in excessive proportions. The ectopic fat deposition syndrome could be supported by the three pieces of evidence that are listed below:

- 1) In mice and humans, lipodystrophy results in ectopic fat deposition in liver, muscle and pancreatic cells and causes insulin resistance and diabetes (77-79).

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2) In most obese patients, lipids infiltrate skeletal muscles, liver, and beta cells, and lipid infiltration is strongly associated with insulin resistance (80-82).

3) Increased fat cell sizes are associated with insulin resistance and diabetes. Large fat cells may be incapable of adapting to high-level energy influx

The essential regulatory mechanism that is known as the endocrine function of adipose tissue is driven by the signaling proteins that are secreted by adipose tissue. These signaling proteins are also referred to by the labels adipocytokines and adipokines; both terminology is used interchangeably. Leptin, adiponectin, resistin, tumor necrosis factor-alpha, and interleukin-6 are all examples of adipokines, which are hormones that are released by fat cells. Other adipokines include resistin (83). Even though individual fat cells only produce exceedingly lesser amounts of adipokines, the total amount of adipokines released into the body may influence the activities of the body because adipose tissue is the largest organ in the body. This is even though individual fat cells only generate exceedingly lesser amounts of adipokines (83). Homeostasis, blood pressure, the metabolism of lipids and glucose, inflammation, and atherosclerosis are all regulated by these signaling proteins, which are also crucial for maintaining homeostasis (83). When recombinant adiponectin is administered to animals, the effects are as follows: an increase in glucose uptake and fat oxidation in the muscles; a decrease in glucose synthesis in the liver; and an increase in insulin sensitivity across the whole of the body. Insulin resistance and diabetes mellitus were healed in adiponectin transgenic mice, as well as a considerable reduction in the body's natural manufacture of glucose. Animals that lack adiponectin, on the other hand, are unable to make insulin receptor substrate (IRS) and have an intolerance to glucose (83).

In humans, it has been shown that levels of the hormone adiponectin in the plasma have links that are opposite to those of obesity, insulin resistance, type 2 diabetes, and metabolic syndrome. On the other hand, it has been shown that these levels have favorable relationships with measures of insulin sensitivity. [Citation needed] (83).

There is a wide variety of adiponectins, and some of them are related to the lipocalin family. Insulin resistance and obesity are two conditions that are connected to each other. Two of the several lipocalins that have been implicated in the relationship between obesity and insulin

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resistance are called LCN2 and retinol binding protein four. Recent additions to the list of adipokines, both lipocalins may now be found on it (84).

Obese persons had greater circulating LCN 2 concentrations than normal weight individuals do, according to the findings of a study that looked at the correlation between serum LCN 2 levels and body mass index (BMI). It was shown to be favorably connected with several anthropometric parameters (such as belly circumference), and it was found to be positively correlated with obesity, insulin resistance, and inflammation in mice and adult humans. These results were observed after correcting for age and gender (72).

A research was conducted with adult patients who were diagnosed with diabetic nephropathy. The participants were followed for a duration of one year. During that time, it was found that the level of LCN 2 in the urine increased during the follow-up, and that this increase was found to be negatively correlated with cystatin C, urea nitrogen, and creatinine with a positive glomerular filtration rate. In addition, this increase was found to have occurred because of a positive glomerular filtration rate. The fact that the research discovered a link between these three parameters and a greater GFR further lends credence to this discovery (85).

It has been shown that the expression of LCN 2 is increased in the process of oxidative damage that occurs in the heart and kidney because of ischemia-reperfusion. [Citation needed] [Citation needed]

(86,87). Studies suggest that LCN 2 is a sensitive biomarker that can provide an early indication of kidney damage; it also has significant correlations with measures of lupus nephritis disease activity; and it may be an important and appropriate biomarker for relapses. All these characteristics make LCN 2 a candidate for the role of an important and appropriate biomarker. Researchers have stated that they came to these conclusions (73,74).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patients who presented themselves to the Pediatric Endocrinology outpatient clinic at Kecioren Training and Research Hospital with the complaint of being overweight and were granted a diagnosis of obesity were enrolled as participants in the research. These forty-three individuals made up the obese group. In addition, there were thirty-two individuals of the same age group who participated in the research. All these patients were healthy and of normal weight (control

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group). Patients that had a history of medication usage (such as steroids or antipsychotics), endocrine pathology (such as Cushing's syndrome or hypothyroidism), or any other reason that may promote obesity were not included in the research. These cases were judged to be obese. These ailments include cardiovascular illness, digestive disease, pulmonary disease, and others like them. When referring to children, being obese was defined as having a body mass index (BMI) that was more than the 95th percentile for both their age and gender. This was taken into consideration when determining the BMI. The knowledge that was gleaned from the study conducted by Bundak and his colleagues was used in the analysis of obesity (88).

At first, a thorough medical examination was performed on each patient who was going to take part in the study. This was done to ensure that the participants were healthy enough to take part. The individual's height was measured using a Harpenden stadiometer that had a measurement accuracy of 0.1 centimeters, and their weight was measured with an SECA scale that had a measurement accuracy of 0.1 kilograms. Both devices were calibrated to within 0.1 of their stated readings. Before calculating the patients' weight, all the patients' clothes were removed, except for the patients' underwear. This was done so that the weight of the patients could be accurately determined. The body mass index (BMI) of a person was calculated by taking their total body weight and dividing it by the square of their height as it was measured (m). The Tanner stage was used to guide the analysis of the data pertaining to the progression of pubescence. In men, pubertal findings include a testicular volume that is more than four milliliters, while in females, pubertal findings include breast growth that has reached Tanner Stage 2 or higher.

Once the patients had fasted for at least 24 hours without consuming any food or liquid, a vein in their arm was pricked to withdraw some of their blood. The levels of total cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL, and HDL, as well as the levels of fasting serum glucose and insulin, were measured using a blood sample that was taken from the patient. Urine samples were taken from both groups at regular intervals of 24 hours. The enzymatic method (Lot No: D426 from Konelab) was used in conjunction with an automated analyzer for the purpose of determining the glucose concentrations present in the fasting serum (Konelab 60I, Thermo Scientific, Finland). Quantification of the insulin level in the fasting state was accomplished using the immunoluminometric (ILMA) method (DiaSorin). To assess the levels of total cholesterol as well as triglycerides, the enzymatic calorimetric method was used (Lot No. B540 and Lot No.

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C186, respectively, from Konelab). The homogeneous enzymatic calorimetric method was used to determine the levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol (lot no. C435, Konelab) (lot no. C136, Konelab). To conduct research on high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP) immunochemistry, the IMMAGE® (Beckman Coulter) method was used.

Urine samples were collected over the course of 24 hours and stored at -80 degrees Celsius to perform the ELISA test, which was then used to calculate the quantity of LCN 2 present in the urine. The Human Lipocalin-2/NGAL Biovender Czech Republic was responsible for the production of the lipocalin kit that was used.

To perform an accurate evaluation of insulin resistance, the "Homaostasis model assessment-insulin resistance" (HOMA-IR) index was used. It was established that the "cut-off" values for insulin resistance occur during pubertal periods (Pubertal HOMA-IR >4). (89). Ultrasounds were performed on the livers of both the obese group and the control group to look for signs of fatty liver disease. The glomerular filtration rate (GFR) was determined for each patient by using the Swartz formula to evaluate the renal function of everyone.

Creatinine clearance (ml/min/1.73 m²) = (k* x patient's height) / serum creatinine

*k = 0.33 in low-birth-weight infants in the first year of life

k = 0.45 in term infants in the first year of life

k = 0.55 in children and adolescent girls

k = 0.70 in adolescent males

Statistical analysis:

The results of the analysis of the data gathered from this research were performed using the SPSS 15.0 programme. The Mann Whitney U Test was used in the context of paired groups for the purpose of determining whether there was a significant difference between the groups because of the results of the normality test on the data. The threshold of significance that was utilized was 0.05, and it was claimed that there was a significant difference between the groups

if p was less than 0.05, and that there was not a significant difference between the groups in the case that p was more than 0.05.

The Chi-Square test was used to investigate the relationships that existed between categorical variables and numerical ones. The threshold of significance utilized was 0.05, and it was indicated that a significant association existed if the p -value was less than 0.05, but that there was not a significant link if the p -value was more than 0.05.

The Pearson correlation test was used to investigate the relationships that existed between the numerical variables. The threshold of significance utilized was 0.05, and if p was less than 0.05, it was determined that there was a significant correlation between the two variables.

4. FINDINGS

The research consisted of a total of seventy-five participants, 43 of whom had been diagnosed with obesity and 32 of whom were healthy. There were twenty-one males (48.8%) and 22 females (51.2%) among the obese patients, while there were 14 males (43.7% of the control group) and 20 females (56.3%) among the obese cases. The obese group had a mean age of 13.13 years (standard deviation: 1.81) whereas the control group had a mean age of 12.94 years (standard deviation: 1.94) The age difference between the two groups was insignificant ($p = 0.490$), showing that there was no meaningful difference. In terms of the ratio of males to females, there was not a significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.839$, $p = 0.084$). The mean body mass index (BMI) of those who were obese ranged from 34.12 to 22.84 kg/m², whereas the mean BMI of those who served as controls was 20.54 to 2.56 kg/m². On comparing the two groups' BMIs, there was a statistically significant gap between them (p less than 0.01). Both body mass index and skinfold thickness were found to be significantly different between the two groups (p 0.01). (Table 2).

Table: 2 - Demographic characteristics of the groups

	Obese Group (n=43)	Control Group (n=32)	<i>p</i>
Age (years)	13.13±1.81	12.94±1.94	0.490

Gender(F/M)	22/21	14/20	0.839/0.084
BMI (kg/m²)	34.12±22.84	20.54±2.56	<0.001
BMI SDS	3.56±6.29	0.45±0.82	<0.001

The levels of cholesterol, glucose, high-density lipoprotein, insulin, cortisol, high-sensitivity CRP, glomerular filtration rate, and LCN 2/creatinine were greater in the obese compared to the control group (p 0.05). It was discovered that the values of glucose, cholesterol, insulin, cortisol, hs-CRP, and LCN 2/creatinine were higher in the obese group, but the values of HDL and GFR were significantly higher in the control group (p 0.05).

In terms of data for TG, LDL, microalbumin, microalbumin/creatinine, and LCN 2, there is not a statistically significant difference between the groups (p>0.05). (Table 3)

Table: 3 -Distribution of Clinical and Laboratory Characteristics of Obese and Control Group Individuals

	Obese n=43	Group Control n=32	Group P
Age(years)	13.13 ± 1.81	12.94 ± 1.94	0.490
BMI (kg/m²)	34.12±22.84	20.54±2.56	<0.001
BMI SDS	3.56±6.29	0.45±0.82	<0.001
Waist Circumference(cm)	100.33±9.48	65.06±3.71	<0.001
Hip Circumference(cm)	105.51±11.36	76.50±7.77	<0.001
Glucose (mg/dL)	89.70±7.67	82.38±5.23	<0.001
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	165.74±35.12	129.94±27.33	<0.001
TG(mg/dL)	120±66.42	99.34±47.78	0.280
LDL(mg/dL)	94.48±28.95	83.59±25.28	0.147
HDL(mg/dL)	42.72±8.47	48.91±17.85	0.045
Insulin(IU/mL)	29.67±21.57	12.06±4.16	<0.001
Cortisol(µg/dL)	9.37±3.52	5.62±0.71	<0.001
hs-CRP(mg/dL)	0.41±0.30	0.01±0.01	<0.001

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GFR(ml/min/1.73)	154.73±26.24	178.27±28.10	<0.001
Microalbumin (mg/day)	17.04±21.92	9.31±7.09	0.428
Microalbumin/Creatinine	0.23±0.34	0.09±0.07	0.096
LCN 2(ng/mL)	2.97±0.70	2.53±1.72	0.830
LCN 2/Creatinine(ng/mg)	4.12±3.01	2.14±2.11	0.004

According to the findings presented by HOMAIR, the presence of insulin resistance was shown to have a correlation that was statistically significant with the groups (p 0.05).

When looking at the community of obese people, the prevalence of insulin resistance is shown to be significantly higher than the incidence of insulin sensitivity 86.67 percent of the time. In the control group, the proportion of individuals who do not have insulin resistance is 92.86 percentage points higher than the percentage of people who do have insulin resistance. This indicates that most people in the control group do not have insulin resistance.

There was a link between the presence of fatty liver and the groups, and this association had the potential to be regarded statistically significant (p less than 0.05). It has been shown that someone falls into the group of obese individuals if they have a fatty liver (Table 4).

Table: 4 - Comparison of HOMA-IR and Fatty Liver in Obese and Control Group Individuals

		GROUP						Statistical analysis	
		OBESE		CONTROL		Total		Chi-Square	P
		n	%	n	%	n	%		
INSULIN RESISTANCE BY HOMAIR	THERE IS	39	86.67	6	13.33	45	one hundred	41,165	<0.001
	NO	2	7.14	26	92.86	28	one hundred		
	Total	41	56.16	32	43.84	73	one hundred		
LIVER LUBRICATION	THERE IS	23	one hundred	0	0.00	23	one hundred	22,235	<0.001
	NO	20	38.46	32	61.54	52	one hundred		
	Total	43	57.33	32	42.67	75	one hundred		

When the findings of the two groups were compared, there was not a clear statistically significant difference ($p>0.05$) in total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein, high-density lipoprotein, glomerular filtration rate, microalbumin, or lactate carboxylase type 2.

There was a statistically significant difference in the levels of glucose, cholesterol, insulin, cortisol, hs-CRP, microalbumin/creatinine, and LCN 2/creatinine when the groups of men were compared ($p 0.05$). The levels of glucose, cholesterol, insulin, cortisol, high-sensitivity C-reactive protein, microalbumin/creatinine, and LCN 2/creatinine were all shown to be significantly elevated in guys who were obese.

In females, there was not a statistically significant difference between the groups in terms of the findings for total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), microalbumin, microalbumin/creatinine, LCN 2, and LCN 2/creatinine ($p>0.05$).

When comparing the groups of females, there was a difference in the levels of glucose, cholesterol, insulin, cortisol, hs-CRP, and GFR that was statistically significant ($p 0.05$).

The levels of glucose, cholesterol, insulin, cortisol, and high-sensitivity C-reactive protein were found to be higher in girls who were classed as obese, whereas the levels of GFR were found to be significantly higher in girls who were classified as having a healthy weight. (Table 5)

Table: 5 -Laboratory Characteristics of Obese and Control Groups by Gender

	Girl		p	Male		p
	Obese	Control		Obese	Control	
Glucose (mg/dL)	87.5±6.83	82.67±5.47	0.033	92±7.98	82±5.08	<0.001
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	163.59±36.82	125.89±27.32	0.002	168.1±33.93	135.14±27.44	0.003
TG(mg/dL)	104.91±56.39	78±23.89	0.183	138.69±73.32	126.79±57.06	0.806
LDL(mg/dL)	97.18±31.94	77.44±27.76	0.135	91.5±25.77	91.5±19.91	0.834

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HDL(mg/dL)	41.77±7.67	52.89±22.8	0.072	43.75±9.36	43.79±5.39	0.334
	1	1				
Insulin(IU/mL)	26.77±11.6	13.18±4.80	<0.00	33.04±29.2	10.62±2.69	<0.00
	1	1	1	3		1
Cortisol(µg/dL)	8.65±3.47	5.67±0.65	<0.00	10.25±3.47	5.55±0.81	<0.00
			1			1
hs-CRP(mg/dL)	0.38±0.26	0.01±0.02	<0.00	0.45±0.34	0.01±0.00	<0.00
			1			1
GFR(ml/min/1.73)	142.13±19.	169.83±20.	<0.00	167.92±26.	189.11±32.	0.074
	35	93	1	38	94	
Microalbumin (mg/day)	21.08±26.6	11.84±7.27	0.765	12.8±14.99	6.07±5.53	0.252
	9					
Microalbumin/Creatinine	0.31±0.44	0.12±0.08	0.786	0.16±0.17	0.05±0.04	0.010
LCN 2(ng/mL)	3.98±3.38	3.01±2.12	0.446	1.90±0.98	1.91±0.65	0.813
LCN 2/Creatinine(ng/mg)	4.12±3.01	2.14±2.11	0.071	3.12±3.10	2.00±1.00	0.010

Those who are obese and those who do not have insulin resistance do not have significantly various levels of glucose, cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), cortisol, hs-CRP, GFR, microalbumin, microalbumin/creatinine, or LCN 2/creatinine ($p > 0.05$).

When comparing people in the obese group who have insulin resistance to those in the obese group who do not have insulin resistance, there is a difference in LCN 2 levels that is statistically significant between the two groups ($p < 0.05$). It has been shown that individuals who suffer from insulin resistance have LCN 2 levels that are noticeably higher than average. (Table 6)

Table: 6 - Laboratory Characteristics of the Obese Group with and without Insulin Resistance

Insulin Resistance

	There is	None	p
Glucose (mg/dL)	90.03±8.31	87.86±4.56	0.794
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	169.12±35.34	146.71±31.87	0.119
TG(mg/dL)	127.96±68.72	95.5±50.61	0.212
LDL(mg/dL)	97.32±29.27	87±24	0.425
HDL(mg/dL)	42±7.56	42.29±6.95	0.615
Insulin(IU/mL)	33.01±22.27	13.44±1.53	<0.001
Cortisol(µg/dL)	9.49±3.51	8.79±3.77	0.488
hs-CRP(mg/dL)	0.38±0.25	0.36±0.34	0.678
GFR(ml/min/1.73)	154.97±25.31	147.56±18.67	0.603
Microalbumin (mg/day)	17.04±23.29	11.33±6.90	0.603
Microalbumin/Creatinine	0.22±0.35	0.27±0.38	0.368
LCN 2(ng/mL)	3.32±2.94	1.66±0.20	0.018
LCN 2/Creatinine(ng/mg)	4.12±3.01	2.01±1.02	0.368

Among the obese population, there was not a correlation that could be considered statistically significant between the insulin resistance groups and the prevalence of fatty liver ($p>0.05$) (Table 7).

Table: 7 - Presence of fatty liver in the Obese and Non-Insulin Resistance Groups

		OBESE						Statistical analysis	
		INSULIN RESISTANCE							
		THERE		NO		Total		Chi-Square	P
		IS		NO		Total			
n	%	n	%	n	%				
LIVER LUBRICATION	NO	0	0.00	2	100.0	2	one hundred	Fisher's Exact	0.685
	Total	34	82.9	7	17.07	4	one hundred		

THERE IS	19	86.36	3	13.64	2	one hundred
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When comparing the hypertension groups in terms of the cortisol value in obese patients, there is a difference that may be considered statistically significant (p 0.05). Those diagnosed with hypertension have cortisol levels that are statistically and clinically significantly greater than those diagnosed without hypertension (Table 8).

Table: 8 -Laboratory Characteristics of the Obese Group with and without Hypertension

	Hypertension		
	There is	None	p
Glucose (mg/dL)	92.16±7.58	87.75±7.31	0.117
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	171.32±36.63	161.13±33.92	0.343
TG(mg/dL)	116.81±50.91	124.45±77.92	0.820
LDL(mg/dL)	100±25.99	89.91±31.01	0.189
HDL(mg/dL)	41.42±6.48	43.78±9.83	0.390
Insulin(IU/mL)	35.81±28.52	24.37±11.20	0.092
Cortisol(µg/dL)	11.06±3.41	7.84±2.90	0.05
hs-CRP(mg/dL)	0.36±0.21	0.46±0.35	0.549
GFR(ml/min/1.73)	152.57±27.12	156.43±25.99	0.533
Microalbumin (mg/day)	13.92±23.06	19.51±21.14	0.282
Microalbumin/Creatinine	0.18±0.39	0.28±0.30	0.160
LCN 2(ng/mL)	3.14±2.47	2.83±2.91	0.203
LCN 2/Creatinine(ng/mg)	4.12±3.01	4.05±3.06	0.353

It was discovered that there is no significant correlation between microalbumin/creatinine values and glucose, insulin, cortisol, hs-CRP, GFR, LCN 2, and LCN 2/creatinine values in the obese group (p>0.05). This was discovered when the relationship between

microalbumin/creatinine levels and clinical and laboratory parameters in the obese group was investigated.

When the relationship between microalbumin/creatinine levels and clinical and laboratory parameters in the control group was examined, it was found that there is no significant correlation between microalbumin/creatinine levels and glucose and insulin levels ($p > 0.05$). This was the conclusion reached when the relationship between microalbumin/creatinine levels and clinical and laboratory parameters in the control group was examined.

There was a substantial positive association found between microalbumin/creatinine values and cortisol, hs-CRP, microalbumin, LCN 2, and LCN 2/creatinine values. On the other hand, there was a significant negative correlation found between GFR values and microalbumin/creatinine values (Table 9).

Table: 9 - The Relationship of Microalbumin/creatinine Levels with Laboratory Parameters in Obese and Control Groups

	Obese		Control	
	Microalbumin/Creatinine			
	r	p	r	p
Glucose (mg/dL)	-0.205	0.188	0.197	0.279
Insulin(IU/mL)	-0.129	0.423	0.336	0.060
Cortisol(µg/dL)	0.028	0.865	0.388	0.028
hs-CRP(mg/dL)	-0.031	0.842	0.401	0.023
GFR(ml/min/1.73)	-0.183	0.241	-0.361	0.042
LCN 2 (ng/mL)	-0.067	0.669	0.625	<0.001
LCN 2/Creatinine(ng/mg)	-0.024	0.876	0.725	<0.001

When the relationship of LCN 2 and LCN 2/creatinine levels with clinical and laboratory parameters in the obese group was examined, there was a significant difference between LCN 2 values and glucose, cholesterol, TG, LDL, HDL, insulin, cortisol, hs-CRP, GFR, microalbumin, and microalbumin/creatinine values. Additionally, there was a significant

difference between LCN 2 values and microalbumin and microalbumin/creatinine values There is no statistically significant connection ($p>0.05$).

The values of glucose, cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein, high-density lipoprotein, insulin, cortisol, hs-CRP, GFR, microalbumin, and microalbumin/creatinine do not have a significant association with each other ($p>0.05$).

When the link between LCN 2 and LCN 2/creatinine levels as well as clinical and laboratory indicators in the control group were investigated, it was shown that there was no significant association between LCN 2 values and the levels of glucose, cholesterol, TG, or cortisol ($p>0.05$). Values of HDL, Insulin, hs-CRP, microalbumin, and microalbumin/creatinine were shown to have a substantial positive association with one another, but values of LCN 2 and LDL and GFR were found to have a significant negative correlation.

There is not a significant link found between the levels of LCN 2/Creatinine, glucose, cholesterol, TG, LDL, cortisol, or GFR ($p>0.05$). Values of HDL, insulin, hs-CRP, microalbumin, and values of microalbumin/creatinine are significantly positively correlated with values of LCN 2/Creatinine. This association is substantial. (Table 10)

Table: 10 - Correlation of LCN 2 and LCN 2/Creatinine Levels with Laboratory Parameters in Obese and Control Groups

	Obese		LCN		Control		LCN	
	LCN 2		2/Creatinine		LCN 2		2/Creatinine	
	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p
Glucose (mg/dL)	0.116	0.458	0.193	0.216	-0.150	0.411	0.082	0.655
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	-0.062	0.696	-0.142	0.369	0.047	0.797	0.086	0.639
TG(mg/dL)	-0.053	0.740	-0.096	0.544	-0.180	0.324	-0.244	0.178

LDL(mg/dL)	0.188	0.23 4	-0.062	0.697	- 0.436	0.01 3	-0.274	0.129
HDL(mg/dL)	- 0.278	0.07 5	-0.091	0.568	0.808	0,00 0	0.591	<0.001
Insulin(IU/mL)	0.113	0.48 1	0.165	0.301	0.619	0,00 0	0.531	0.002
Cortisol(µg/dL)	0.057	0.72 6	0.087	0.594	0.222	0.22 3	0.288	0.111
hs-CRP(mg/dL)	0.091	0.56 0	0.059	0.709	0.796	0,00 0	0.555	0.001
GFR(ml/min/1.73)	- 0.036	0.81 7	0.045	0.775	- 0.384	0.03 0	-0.283	0.116
Microalbumin (mg/day)	0.018	0.90 9	0.021	0.894	0.694	0,00 0	0.629	<0.001
Microalbumin/Creatinine	- 0.067	0.66 9	-0.024	0.876	0.625	0,00 0	0.725	<0.001

5. DISCUSSION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), obesity is defined as an increase in the amount of fat that is present in the body composition to a level that is likely to have a negative impact on human health. Obesity is a health issue that is becoming more widespread all over the globe, particularly in industrialized nations, and its prevalence is on the rise. According to the results of the MONICA research, which was conducted by the World Health Organization (WHO) in six distinct locations throughout Asia, Africa, and Europe over the course of 12 years, it was determined that the prevalence of obesity has increased by 10–30% in only 10 years (14).

The increasing prevalence of obesity is cause for concern, particularly among children and teenagers. The yearly rise in the prevalence of obesity among children is expanding. It is stated that the prevalence of obesity in children now is ten times greater than the levels seen in the 1970s now, which we have reached today (14).

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The development of obesity in childhood is associated with an increased risk of developing a variety of metabolic and cardiovascular illnesses in later life (90). Obesity is often linked to several health conditions, including high blood pressure, high cholesterol levels, insulin resistance, and hyperinsulinemia, all of which are risk factors for coronary artery disease and type 2 diabetes (91).

The fast rise in obesity, as well as the illness and death that are directly associated to obesity, has prompted scientists to do further research on adipose tissue. It is now generally understood that the adipose tissue is not only responsible for the storage of fat, but that it also functions as an active endocrine organ. This was not the case in the past. It is well recognized that it maintains homeostasis with the mediators that are released by adipose tissue, that it controls blood pressure, the metabolism of fat and glucose, inflammation, and atherosclerosis, and that it fulfills these functions (92). Lipocalin-2 is a glycoprotein that has a molecular weight of 25 kDa and is also known as NGAL (neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin). It is produced in adipose tissue and liver and has more than 20 different subtypes (72). It was first found in the kidney cells of mice as well as in the granules of human neutrophils. It has been shown that in addition to neutrophils, it may also be generated from the liver, lung, kidney, adipose tissue, and other organs (93-97). It has been hypothesized that lipocalin-2 plays a significant role in the processes that lead to inflammation, obesity, and the development of insulin resistance (72, 98, 99). Nevertheless, the precise function of lipocalin-2 is not yet understood. It has been shown to have metabolic effects in obesity, and it may also be employed as a significant determinant in acute renal damage and urinary tract infections (72, 75, 100-104). This is according to the research that has been conducted on this topic. Despite all this knowledge, the function that lipocalin-2 plays in the etiopathogenesis of obesity is not entirely understood, and contradicting findings have been described in the published research. According to Wang et al. research, the LCN 2 level in adult obese individuals was shown to be greater than in non-obese patients and was found to connect with fasting insulin and HOMA-IR (insulin resistance) (72). Yan et al. The level of LCN 2 was shown to be greater in obese rats that participated in an experimental investigation than in rats that did not participate in the study (100). In the research conducted by Panidis and colleagues, it was discovered that the serum LCN 2 level in obese women who had been diagnosed with PCOS was greater than the level reported in the non-obese group. (105) . Despite these results, Choi et al. (106) found no statistically significant

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difference between the blood LCN 2 levels of obese and non-obese subjects in their investigation. There are two studies that have been conducted to determine the amount of LCN 2 in obese children, and the findings of these studies are comparable to the findings of research conducted on adults (107,108). The first of them was a research project that was conducted on prepubertal adolescents who were obese, and it was discovered that their blood LCN 2 level was greater than the control group (108). In a different research that was conducted on youngsters, it was discovered that the blood LCN 2 levels in the obese group were statistically considerably lower than those observed in the control group. (107) . Likewise, when we look at the research that has been published, we do not find any studies that look at LCN 2 in 24-hour urine in either adults or children. Since lipocalin-2 is a relatively novel glycoprotein, there are few articles on this topic that can be found in the relevant literature. The purpose of our research was to demonstrate the function that LCN 2, a novel glycoprotein associated with obesity, plays in juvenile obesity, as well as that protein's connection to anthropometric and laboratory data, as well as its connection to insulin resistance.

In the research that we conducted, the 24-hour urine LCN 2/creatinine levels of the fat group and the control group were compared with participants of the same age and gender. The results showed that the LCN 2/creatinine levels in the obese group were statistically higher. As compared to the control group, the obese group had considerably higher levels of blood glucose, cholesterol, insulin, cortisol, and high-sensitivity CRP. They also had a significantly larger waist circumference and hip circumference.

While it has been shown that serum LCN 2 level is related to glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity, it has also been demonstrated that this level does not rise in connection with obesity and does not exhibit a positive link with the parameters of metabolic syndrome (10,31). LCN 2 was shown to have a positive correlation with BMI, blood glucose, insulin resistance index, and triglyceride level, while having a negative correlation with HDL (10), according to the findings of a research that was conducted on adult subjects who were obese. In contrast to this research, another study indicated that it did not have a correlation with the indices of metabolic syndrome (body mass index, waist circumference, blood pressure, total cholesterol, and HDL-C). In the same research, correlations between LCN 2 and cholesterol, creatinine, and hs-CRP were detected in individuals diagnosed with metabolic syndrome (31). A negative correlation was found between serum LCN 2 levels and BMI-SDS values in a study that was conducted with

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obese children in the pediatric and adolescent age group (13). However, no significant correlation was found between LCN 2 values and glucose, cholesterol, TG, LDL, HDL, insulin, cortisol, hs-CRP, GFR, or microalbumin values in either the obese or control groups. The study was conducted with obese children in the pediatric and

It was discovered that the amount of LCN 2 in the urine collected over a period of 24 hours was statistically elevated in the group of obese people who also had insulin resistance.

When we look at obese individuals who have hypertension and obese patients who do not have hypertension, we find that the 24-hour urine LCN 2 levels of the two groups are identical to one another. It was shown that individuals who were obese and had hypertension had considerably elevated levels of cortisol in their serum.

Insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes are both conditions that may be caused by obesity, which is a well-known risk factor. In addition, unlike diabetes, obesity is linked to glomerular hyperfiltration, the development of glomerulosclerosis, and kidney failure. All these conditions may occur on their own. It has been reported that kidney endothelial dysfunction and increased renin-angiotensin system activity play a role in the development of microalbuminuria (9,10). When we looked through the available research, we did not find any studies that examined the relationship between microalbuminuria and LCN 2 level in 24-hour urine. In the research that we conducted, we did not find any significant link between the values of microalbumin/creatinine and the levels of glucose, insulin, cortisol, hs-CRP, GFR, LCN 2, or LCN 2/creatinine in either of the groups that were obese. When the association between microalbumin/creatinine levels and clinical and laboratory indicators in the control group was investigated, it was found that there was no significant correlation between the levels of glucose and insulin and the microalbumin/creatinine values. However, there is a significant negative correlation between GFR values, while there is a significant positive correlation between microalbumin/creatinine values and cortisol, hs-CRP, LCN 2, and LCN 2/creatinine values. Additionally, there is a significant positive correlation between microalbumin/creatinine values and LCN 2/creatinine values.

In conclusion, it was discovered that the ratio of LCN 2 to creatinine was greater in obese children compared to the control group, which suggests that it relates to increased lipocalin levels in obese persons who have insulin resistance. The amount of LCN 2 in obese children's

urine collected over a period of 24 hours was investigated in our study, making it the first study in the existing body of research to do so. In addition to this, the assessment of our research is hindered by the low total number of patients. Larger series in the childhood age range are required to get a deeper comprehension of the part that lipocalin plays in the development of obesity and insulin resistance.

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